

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe:
Demonstration of water-related innovation packages

REPLICATION GUIDE

How to achieve transformational adaptation to climate change in your local region

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Introduction

Purpose of this guide

The impacts of climate change are here and now. The consequences on people, prosperity and the planet will only intensify in the upcoming years. To prepare for this uncertain future, transformational adaptation is necessary.

Within this replication guide, we will offer an overview of the essential steps and processes you might need for making transformational adaptation happen in your own communities. Based on the overall structure of the [Regional Adaptation Support Tool \(RAST\)](#), we guide you in how to discover opportunities with local stakeholders and offer methods and tools to implement solutions and evaluate your progress.

To help explain how this can be achieved in practice, we showcase an adaptation process in Gjøvik municipality. Our hope is that this guide will inspire other cities and regions across Europe to explore the power of transformational adaptation to climate change.

Who is it for?

The main target groups for this replication guide are local and regional government entities, as well as policy makers, across Europe.

We also expect advisors, process facilitators and scientific and industrial partners to benefit from the guide.

Additional info and resources: [Regional Adaptation Support Tool \(RAST\)](#)

About the TransformAr project

This Replication Guide is primarily based on the experiences from and tools developed within the TransformAr project but aims to serve as a foundation for the broader community aiming to implement transformational adaptation.

TransformAr is an EU-funded project that aims to create solutions to introduce large-scale and disruptive adaptive transformational processes to reduce climate related impacts in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. This transformational adaptation is being triggered by a co-innovation process that aims to co-create adaptation pathways and implement solutions, taking into account stakeholder inputs as well as scientific and socio-economic indicators.

Gathering 22 partners from 11 countries, among 6 demonstrator sites and 1 replicator site, the project's findings contributes to the EU's strategy on climate change adaptation.

 Project Countries
 Demonstrators

Additional info and resources:
[TransformAr Project web page](#)

What is transformational adaptation?

Figure 1: Incremental versus transformational adaptation

Ref: Understanding Transformational Adaptation A shared vision across EU Horizon projects
January 2025

There are many strategies for dealing with climate change. For example, in response to floods, a community might build higher dams or provide favourable loan conditions to help rebuild damaged homes. However, these actions do not fundamentally reduce the risk of more severe storms or future floods. Additionally, socio-economic constraints limit the indefinite implementation of these measures.

Rather than these "incremental adaptations," communities could consider transforming their social-ecological system to become more resilient to uncertain risks. This could involve relocating homes or crop fields to different areas or implementing other measures that significantly change the system's ecological and social characteristics. Such changes address the root causes of vulnerability to climate change.

Because these transformative adaptation measures are more extensive and intrusive, their implementation can encounter several barriers, including lack of social or political support. This is why involving and engaging stakeholders is crucial to facilitate and co-develop adaptation strategies that are endorsed and accepted by the local community.

Additional info and resources:

[IPCC Sixth Assessment Report](#)

[Policy brief, understanding transformational adaptation](#)

How to Use the Guide Effectively

Use the guide as a framework and general approach to your own, local transformational adaptation journey.

Use the resources referenced on each page to get additional information and access practical tools.

Use the case study as inspiration on how the framework can be used in a real-world environment.

Use the colour scheme and links for quick and easy navigation of the guide and relevant resources.

But remember to:

- Make adaptations to local conditions and scenarios
- Use only the tools that make sense for your specific situation. Some tools have similar outcomes, and some tools can be used together for increased effect

Doing transformational adaptation in theory

The Regional Adaptation Support Tool

As a high-level framework for this guide, and for the transformational adaptation process in general, we recommend you use the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST).

The tool is designed to assist local and regional authorities with climate change adaptation strategies and plans, covering development, implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and updates. RAST offers practical guidance in six steps, aligned with key features of climate adaptation policy processes. This flexible and iterative tool adapts to the policy-making process and the unique local context of your local or regional authority.

This Replication Guide leverages the structure of RAST and combines it with practical handbooks and tools developed in the TransformAr project.

Additional info and resources: [Regional Adaptation Support Tool \(RAST\)](#)

Figure 2: Overview Regional Adaptation Support Tool
 Ref: European Environment Agency website

Step 1 – Preparing the ground for adaptation

Engaging stakeholders

Finding and involving the correct stakeholders across various sectors is crucial to achieve transformational adaptation. This includes local representatives from agriculture, development agencies, utility companies, universities, research centres, NGOs, the private sector, and citizens.

Involving a diverse cross-section of the community, including different viewpoints, genders, and age groups, is essential. Address social vulnerability by identifying and involving vulnerable groups in the planning process, offering capacity-building support from the start.

Once key stakeholders are identified, understand their interests and needs, and establish clear roles and responsibilities. Develop a stakeholder management strategy to ensure transparency and create a flexible, measurable engagement strategy that can be continually reviewed.

The workshops and tools developed for use in TransformAr have been designed with heavy stakeholder participation in mind, preparing the ground for a co-innovation ecosystem.

Additional info and resources:

RAST Step 1 – [Preparing the ground for adaptation](#)

TransformAr - [Playbook for transformational adaptation](#)

TransformAr - [Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines](#)

TransformAr - [Stakeholder matrix and Innovation](#)

TransformAr - [Best practice – Stakeholder management](#)

Workshop Format

The TransformAr project recommends using a workshop format for most stakeholder activities, as this constitutes the most efficient way to involve multiple stakeholders to share their insights. Session duration, as well as group configuration, is key to successful outcomes.

Step 2– Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities

Figure 3: Components of climate risks

Ref: European Environment Agency website, Adapted from IPCC, 2023

Climate risk arises from local conditions such as climate hazards, exposure, and vulnerability. Essential adaptation measures and policies aim to reduce risk, limit impacts, and enhance resilience. Effective local and regional adaptation planning requires understanding key factors for a comprehensive climate risk assessment.

In the TransformAr Playbook, two stakeholder workshop sessions are devoted to finding and prioritising risks and assessing their impact.

Workshop session I: Climate Perception, Challenges and Existing Solutions

In the first workshop, the objective is to determine the priorities of local stakeholders. Using the personal and local experiences from stakeholders, risk factors and challenges are identified.

Workshop session II: Climate vulnerability, Impacts and Projections

In the second workshop, the objective is to determine the key risks and impacts to be addressed based on scientific models and data. Risk prioritisation and impact assessment are the desired outputs.

Additional info and resources:

RAST Step 2 – [Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities](#)

TransformAr - [Playbook for transformational adaptation](#)

TransformAr - [Climate Impacts Portal](#)

TransformAr - [Economic evaluation of CC & loss damage functions for KCS](#)

TransformAr - [Climate cost assessment](#)

TransformAr workshop methodology for step 2 and 3

The overall objective of all three sessions: to co-construct adaptation pathways, made up of a sequence of decision-points and measures allowing for decision making in a specific region.

A framework has been put in place across all 3 sessions to help collect and register the necessary components to begin driving transformation adaptation.

Additional info and resources: [TransformAr-Playbook for transformational adaptation](#)

Figure 4: TransformAr's workshop methodology
Ref: TransformAr Playbook for transformational adaptation

Step 3 – Identifying adaptation options

Workshop session III: Vision solutions and Way forward

In the third workshop, the desired outcome is adaptation pathways. Based on the results from workshops I and II, the workshop participants use inspiring content such as a catalogue of solutions and moodboards to produce first a transformational vision, and then a list of measures. These measures are then structured into an adaptation pathways map, showing a way forward.

These pathways are sequences of actions that can be progressively implemented based on future dynamics. A key aspect of this approach is that it addresses one of the major challenges faced by decision-makers regarding climate change: uncertainty. Adaptation pathways can offer alternative routes to achieve a defined objective or strategic outcome.

The TransformAr [Playbook for transformational adaptation](#) provides the essential tools to develop and envision these adaptation pathways for a wide range of community systems.

Additional info and resources:

RAST Step 3 - [Identifying adaptation options](#)

TransformAr - [Playbook for transformational adaptation](#)

TransformAr - [Catalogue tool to identify best available solutions](#)

ADAPTATION PATHWAYS MAP

Figure 5: Adaptation Pathways Map

Ref: TransformAr Playbook for transformational adaptation.

Adapted from Zandvoort et al. (2017): Adaptation pathways in planning for uncertain climate change: Applications in Portugal, the Czech Republic and the Netherlands. Environmental Science and Policy 78 (2017) 18–26.

Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options

The measures from the adaptation pathways will provide you with several adaptation options. But often there will be local, practical matters and real-world constraints to consider before operationalisation.

Choosing the solutions to implement is necessary before you can start your transformational adaptation journey. When selecting solutions, we use a **multi-criteria analysis**.

For a step-by-step guide to this analysis, we recommend the TransformAr **Toolkit for adaptive action planning**. The workshop format is used for this step as well, to ensure multi-stakeholder and citizen input and ownership.

The TransformAr project has developed several tools that could be useful in assessing different criteria.

Additional info and resources:

[RAST Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options](#)
[TransformAr Toolkit for adaptive action planning](#)
[TransformAr Transformational adaptation scorecard](#)
[TransformAr Avoided Damages Framework](#)
[TransformAr Socio-economic impact tool](#)
[TransformAr Results on the public acceptance and preferences](#)
[TransformAr Report on willingness to pay for solutions](#)
[TransformAr Sustainability profiles of solutions](#)
[TransformAr Sustainability rating methodology](#)

Workshop session: Multi-Criteria Analysis

Having clear and pre-defined criteria will help decision makers and stakeholder select the right solutions. Examples of criteria that can be used, are:

- Effectiveness
- Feasibility
- Flexibility
- Cost
- Co-benefits
- Social acceptability
- Associated risks

Step 5 – Implementing adaptation policies and actions

After identifying key risks, setting adaptation priorities and objectives, and selecting suitable solutions, it's time to **implement** them. You can do this through standalone adaptation action plans or by integrating them into broader organisational plans.

An operational action plan, as described by the TransformAr Toolkit for adaptive action planning, should include elements such as specific actions, timelines, responsibilities, and monitoring mechanisms to ensure effective implementation. The action plan should also include actions for the integration of adaptation measures into existing programmes and strategies.

Further, it's important to **secure funding** or financing for measures before finalising your action plan. This ensures sustainability and successful implementation.

Additional info and resources:

RAST Step 5 – [Implementing adaptation policies and actions](#)

TransformAr [Toolkit for adaptive action planning](#)

TransformAr [Catalogue of solutions](#)

TransformAr [Bankability reports](#)

Workshop session: Operational Action Plan

Development of the Operational Action plan is best achieved through a multi-stakeholder workshop format.

For a successful implementation we recommend that all solutions be adapted to local conditions and needs, as well as integrating them into existing governance frameworks, policies and programs.

Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

This step is vital for keeping your adaptation plan and measures on course and achieving the desired outcomes. It establishes a structured approach to monitor progress, assess the results of adaptation actions, and learn from experience.

Although presented as a separate step, monitoring, evaluation, and learning should be **integrated throughout the entire adaptation process**. For instance; Key Performance Indicators should be developed alongside the action plan in step 5. Further, baseline monitoring or data should be established before solutions are implemented, to ensure comparative assessments and impact monitoring.

For increased learning effect, we recommend using a lot of the same tools and calculations that were employed in Step 4.

These activities should be considered continuous and thus **integrated into operational routines**.

Additional info and resources:
 RAST Step 6 – [Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning](#)
 TransformAr [Transformational adaptation scorecard](#)
 TransformAr [Avoided Damages Framework](#)
 TransformAr [Socio-economic impact tool](#)
 TransformAr [Consolidation of TransformAr’s results](#)

Figure 6: Overview Step 6 Monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL)
 Ref: European Environment Agency website

Doing transformational adaptation in real life - Case study: Gjøvik municipality

So how do you use this six-step process – in real life?

In this part of the Replication Guide, we will show how Gjøvik municipality used the processes and tools developed and provided by the TransformAr project to make their own transformational adaptation journey.

We have used only the tools that made sense to us at the time, and we have adapted both tools and solutions freely. Some of our experiences from each step are highlighted in green and red boxes.

What went well?

What could we have done better?

About Gjøvik

Gjøvik is a mid-sized municipality on the shores of lake Mjøsa in the interior of Norway. The city boasts over 30 000 inhabitants and is a centre of industry, higher education and culture.

In the TransformAr project, Gjøvik's role has been that of a replicator demonstrator.

Source photo: Gjøvik municipality

Additional info and resources: [Gjøvik municipality web page](#)

The main local challenges related to climate change

Urban flooding

Source photo: Gjøvik municipality

Flooding of waterways

Source photo: Gjøvik municipality

Contaminants and nutrients decreasing the lake water quality

Source photo: Oppland Arbeiderblad, Jan Strandbakke

Step 1 – Preparing the ground for adaptation

Engaging stakeholders

With the TransformAr workshop format in mind, we gathered 50 stakeholders from about 20 different organisations. Given the limited availability of participants, we decided to conduct workshop sessions I, II, and III consecutively within a single 7-hour day.

What went well?

Using existing collaboration structures, as well as reaching out to new and relevant stakeholders, we were able to gather over 50 stakeholders from different sectors for these initial workshop sessions.

- 32 Local government representatives from 6 different municipalities
- 1 Local policy maker
- 3 Regional government representatives
- 4 National government representatives
- 8 Private sector (business) representatives
- 3 Scientists

Stakeholder interest in participating was high, due to a flooding event just weeks prior to the workshops.

Source photo: Gjøvik municipality

What could we have done better?

Ideally, we wanted even higher stakeholder participation, but practical constraints, scheduling conflicts as well as stakeholders not prioritising the invitation limited the number.

We had no real stakeholder engagement plan that went beyond step 3. Thus, it became challenging to keep stakeholders up to date on the solutions selection and implementation.

No citizens were engaged in the early phases of the project.

Step 2 – Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities

Presentations of existing knowledge from subject matter experts

Workshop sessions I and II are all about developing a shared understanding of existing risks, solutions, challenges and impacts. A lot of these topics were already well explored for our city and region, so we decided to convert session I and II from workshop format to presentations from subject matter experts. In our view, this was a more effective use of stakeholder time. The result was the same, though: **shared understanding and knowledge**.

What could we have done better?

The presentations in session II were from international scientists in the TransformAr project and were conducted online and in English. We believe the outcome from session II would have been even greater if it had been presented in person and in the native language of the stakeholders.

What went well?

- Time-effective format that was easy to organise.
- Subject matter experts were easy to recruit to this task.

Source photos: Gjøvik municipality

Step 2 – Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities

START	SUBJECT	PRESENTER AND TIME
08:15	Registration and coffee	Facilitators
08:30	Welcome	Mayor of Gjøvik (5')
	Background and goals for the day	Facilitators (5')
08:40	Session I - Climate perception, challenges and existing solutions Climate profile and Risk assessment for county Regional plans for climate change adaptation and civil society risk Principles for climate change adaptation Climate change adaptation in Gjøvik municipality Q&A	County Governor (15') County Council (15') Norwegian water and Energy Directorate (10') Gjøvik municipality (20') Facilitators (10')
09:50	Coffee break	
10:10	Session II - Climate vulnerability, impacts and projections Biophysical intermediary impacts and projections Economic impacts Q&A	PIK, CMCC (30') E3 Modelling (20') Facilitators (10')

Table 1: Workshop agenda for sessions I and II

Source: Gjøvik municipality

Step 2 – Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities

Some of the outcomes from this step

LIKELY INCREASE	
 Heavy Precipitation	Episodes of heavy rainfall are expected to increase significantly in both intensity and frequency. This will also lead to more surface water.
 Extreme Rainfall	More and larger rain floods are expected, and in smaller streams and rivers, an increase in flood discharge must be anticipated.
 Landslides, floods	Increased Risk Due to Higher Precipitation Levels
POSSIBLE / LIKELY INCREASE	
 Drought	Despite more summer precipitation, higher temperatures and increased evaporation may lead to an increased risk of drought during the summer.
 Ice Movement	Shorter ice-cover seasons, more frequent winter ice movements, and ice movements occurring further upstream in the watercourses.
 Snow Avalanches	With a warmer and wetter climate, it will more often rain on snow-covered ground. This may reduce the risk of dry snow avalanches and increase the risk of wet snow avalanches in avalanche-prone areas.
 clay landslides	Increased erosion due to heavy rainfall, along with increased flooding in rivers and streams, may trigger more quick clay landslides.

Figure 7: Summary of main regional climate risks

Source: Climate Profile Innlandet, Norwegian Centre for Climate Services

Summary

TransformAr Workshop II: Gjøvik – Climate vulnerability, Impacts and Projections

According to projections, **Gjøvik** is likely to deal with

Figure 8: Summary of climate vulnerability, impacts and projections for Gjøvik.

Source: Presentation from Fred Hattermann, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research

Process tip for session II

If you don't have scientists on hand like we did, we recommend using the [TransformAr Climate Impacts Portal](#) for the latest climate data and projections for your region.

Step 3 – Identifying adaptation options

Workshop session III in groups

We divided the workshop participants into working groups of 4-5 people, plus a group facilitator. Each group decided which specific climate challenge they wanted to work on finding adaptation options for.

Using the pre-defined canvases from the TransformAr Playbook, the groups worked their way through the necessary 5 workshop exercises (see workshop agenda below) to arrive at the desired result of relevant actions per risk level.

Source photos: Gjøvik municipality

What went well?

The compact and effective workshop format was easy to put together using the templates from the TransformAr playbook. We chose to **adapt the templates** into local language beforehand.

The groups chose a **variety** of challenges to work on; water quality and pollution, draughts, biological diversity and flood damages.

We **prioritised during the session**. Adaptation pathways were not developed for droughts and biodiversity, as these were not considered major risks and challenges from the previous step.

What could we have done better?

The time-compacted group workshop format proved ineffective in compiling the results into **adaptation pathways**. This had to be completed after the workshops, using a small group of subject matter experts from the municipality.

Step 3 – Identifying adaptation options

START	SUBJECT	PRESENTER AND TIME
12:00	<p>Part 3 – Vision, solutions and way forward</p> <p>Introduction to group workshop:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the indicators to assess risk evolution • Characterize each risk level • Characterize critical thresholds 	<p>Facilitators</p> <p>10'</p> <p>15'</p> <p>25'</p> <p>20'</p>
13.10	Coffee Break	
13.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation vision • Identify relevant actions per risk level 	<p>20'</p> <p>40'</p>
14.30	<p>Results and evaluation</p> <p>Plenary session</p>	Facilitators
15.00	End	

Table 2: Workshop agenda for session III

Source: Gjøvik municipality

Step 3 – Identifying adaptation options

Figure 9: Step outcome: Adaptation pathways flooding and water quality scenarios
 Source: Gjøvik municipality

Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options

Multi-Criteria Analysis

Having identified several potential solutions in three different categories, the time had come to assess and select.

We had one main criterion, which was **TransformAr project constraints**. Some solutions had been pre-determined in the project by our demonstrator partner Lappeenranta city. Luckily, these fit perfectly with our adaptation pathways.

Other criteria we used in this analysis were:

- **Feasibility**; Is it possible given technical limitations and existing regulations? Or is it already part of existing strategies and plans?
- **Funding**; Do we have funding available for this solution?
- **Cost vs. benefit**; Will the solution have sufficient impact in relation to the resources spent?
- **Co-benefits**; Will the solution have impact on other problems and use cases as well?

What could we have done better?

More in-depth exploration of every assessment criteria for every solution is always possible when making choices like this.

What went well?

We used a variety of techniques and activities to make the necessary assessments.

- A technical and commercial **feasibility study** for the citizen app showed that we should not use the exact same technical solution as our project demonstrator partner Lappeenranta.
- **Co-benefit analysis** for the citizen app showed several other use-cases for this app within our own organization, like road operations and unwanted biodiversity.
- **The Nature Smart Cities Business Model** was used to do cost-benefit analyses for nature-based solutions for urban storm water.
- Application for additional **funding** for a nature-based solution was unsuccessful, so we had to postpone this solution and change some elements.
- The main infrastructure solution of storm water pipe separation was already part of the **municipal strategy and action plans for infrastructure renewal**, so, we did not need to include it in the action plan for this project.
- The regulatory and legal solutions were not feasible for the municipality to attempt, as this is **decided on a national level**. However, doing a **study on the willingness to pay** would provide lawmakers with additional data.
- To further explore the financial solutions, we also participated in the TransformAr collection of data on **insurance schemes for natural disasters**.

Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options

Figure 10: Part of the Multi-criteria analysis: Nature Smart Cities Business Model cost-benefit analysis for one of the nature-based solutions

Source: Gjøvik municipality and University of Antwerp

Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options

Selected Parameters

Currency	€	BASELINE SCENARIO	BRENNERIGATA LIVING STI
	Water retention	546,77 m3/yr	2137,30 m3/yr
	Micro-climate Regulation	Outdoor: 1,03°C red.	Outdoor: 0,7°C red.
 SW - Index 0,84			
	Aesthetic appreciation		
	Does this scenario provide an aesthetically attractive place to live or work in?	Not at all	To a great extent
	Does this scenario include an attractive mix of different landscape elements?	To a limited extent	To some extent
	Does this scenario create, or add to, a sense of place and visual identity?	To a limited extent	To a great extent

Financial Information

Figure 10: Part of the Multi-criteria analysis: Nature Smart Cities Business Model cost-benefit analysis for one of the nature-based solutions
Source: Gjøvik municipality and University of Antwerp

Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options

Figure 11: Step outcome: Pathways and selected solutions

Source: Gjøvik municipality

Step 5 – Implementing adaptation policies and actions

Separate Operational Action Plans for each solution

Having selected solutions that were not codependent or simultaneous, we decided that integrating the solutions implementation into our existing plans was more effective than having an overall action plan for all solutions.

- **The Citizen app** was acquired, adapted and deployed as a combined effort of the Department of Technical Services, and their plans for service improvement.
- **The Storm Water Monitoring** was acquired and implemented as part of the plans of the Department of Water and Sanitation.
- **The Choice experiment on citizens' willingness to pay** was conducted in cooperation with our TransformAr project partners and was handled within the scope and plans of that project.
- **The Storm Water Pipe Separation and Renewal** was already in our plans for infrastructure renewal.

However, the monitoring plan for these solutions was developed comprehensively as part of the TransformAr project.

What went well?

We conducted a **service design process** for the citizen app, developing service blueprints and prototyping a flood reporting service as well as other citizen use cases.

Thorough **change management** within the municipality was necessary to make employees change work processes to fit with the citizen app.

Integration into existing plans was easy, as framework such as ownership, political backing and funding was already in place.

Using **existing contracts** and supplier relationships reduced time spent in the purchasing and implementation phases.

What could we have done better?

Long-term impact monitoring should have been integrated into existing municipal climate plans – not just into the project plans.

The multi-stakeholder workshop format was not used in this step, as we employed existing municipal structures for efficiency. Would **involving more stakeholders** have led to better plans?

Change management within our own organization proved more difficult and extensive than we anticipated.

Step 5 – Implementing adaptation policies and actions

One of the step outcomes: Service blueprint for the use of the citizen app in reporting of flooding and other anomalies.

Step in the citizen's service journey (Touchpoints)	1. Error is detected	2. Error reported	3. Reception and routing	4. Status in progress	5. Feedback after correction
Residents					
	Actions Observing an error. Want to report the error.	2. Error reported Reporting errors to the municipality (various channels).	3. Reception and routing Receives (maybe) a general automated response.	4. Status in progress Asking for status.	5. Feedback after correction Asking for status.
	Problems/Questions Does the municipality already know about this error?	Where can I report issues? There are many different channels.	Has my error message been recorded and assessed?	When will it be fixed? Who is responsible?	Has it been fixed? Was my error message helpful?
	Customer experience for citizens 				
Service center					
	Actions Answers the phone call. Guides the resident.	2. Error reported Answers the phone call. Guides the resident.	3. Reception and routing Recording errors for household. Transferring the call.	4. Status in progress goods on the phone call. May transfer the call.	5. Feedback after correction goods on the phone call. May transfer the call.
	Problems Are dependent on messages from citizens to find errors	Is the error known? Long telephone queue during challenging weather.	The citizen should handle this themselves.	When will it be arranged? Who is responsible?	
Technical operations, administration					
	Actions Receives and assesses messageSends to the correct executor.		3. Reception and routing Receives and assesses messageSends to the correct executor.	4. Status in progress Etterspør status.	5. Feedback after correction Etterspør status.
	Problems Are dependent on messages from citizens to find errors	There are too many channels to keep up with.	Insufficient / incorrect information in the error message.	When will it be fixed?	Has it been fixed? Has the bug reporter been notified?
Technical operation, performing					
	Actions Receiving assignments. Prioritization of assignments.		3. Reception and routing Receiving assignments. Prioritization of assignments.	4. Status in progress Performing the task (correcting the mistake).	
	Problems Are dependent on messages from citizens to find errors		Many orders in the queue.	Few resources in relation to the amount of assignments. Long response time.	Neither the time nor the desire to document or log.
Technology / Channel					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 					

Figure 12: Citizen App Service Blueprint
Source: Gjøvik municipality

Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

Category	Indicator	Unit of measure	Non-technical description
Citizens' awareness and behaviour	Willingness to pay	% with private storm water measures on their plot/house	Citizens' willingness to pay for storm water solutions or storm water taxation. Have they installed the actual solutions?
	Risk awareness	<To be determined>	A number of or a combination of questions from the choice experiment can be used to indicate "awareness"; perceived flood frequency, threats to water quality, number of "Don't know"s, etc.
Health and environment	Improved lake water quality after storm water events	MPN / 100 ml (E-coli and intestinal enterococci) after a certain amount of precipitation	Reduced overflow (NSB and SWM) will reduce the amount of sewage going into the lake. Will show up in water samples analysed in lab.
Economic	Reduced storm water and flood damages (insurance)	NOK / year	Amount of insurance damages paid as a result of floodings
	Reduced storm water and flood damages (insurance)	Reported incidents / year	Number of floodings reported to insurance companies

Table 3: Impact Key Performance Indicators

Source: Gjøvik municipality

Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

One of the step outcomes: Transformational Adaptation Scorecard, indicating if our solution is truly transformational.

Figure 13: Transformational Adaptation Scorecard
Source: Gjøvik municipality and University of Antwerp

Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

Solution monitoring is easier than impact monitoring

Monitoring solution use or effectiveness gives us tangible micro-level data like liters per second, hours of storm water overflow or citizen incidents reported and response times for these.

Monitoring adaptation impact on a macro level is much more difficult because there are a lot of other variables in play, and because it is difficult to determine the actual impact of each one. For instance, the amount of rain will probably have a lot more impact on storm water damages, than our monitoring station or nature-based solution.

What went well?

We developed KPIs for each solution as well as the overall impact **early in the adaptation process**. This helped us to focus on what's important and gave us the opportunity to get **baseline data** before solution implementation.

Tools like the **Transformational Adaptation Scorecard and Avoided damages framework** were used as input to our evaluation and learning process.

What could we have done better?

Due to the publication date of this guide being close to our solutions implementation, we have not really had the time to do any **real evaluation and learning**. That will come later.

Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

One of the step outcomes: Avoided damage framework, evaluating reduced damages prevented by implementing solutions.

Avoided damages:

Near future (2040-2070)

- **Total avoided damages:** Long-term avoided damages range from –48.1% to –47.1%, while short-term avoided damages are –23.6%.
- **Direct damages:** The effectiveness of the solutions (SWMM and URB) increases dramatically in all scenarios by at least 28.7%.
- **Indirect damages:** Avoided damages are higher than for direct damages because citizens are willing to pay for the most effective adaptation measures.

Far future (2070 – 2100)

- **Total avoided damages:** Long-term avoided damages range from –50.4% to –46.6%, while short-term avoided damages remain –23.6%.
- **Direct damages:** The solutions show a significant increase in effectiveness with improvements of at least 28.1%.
- **Indirect damages:** Avoided damages are greater for indirect damages because citizens are willing to pay more for the most effective adaptation measures.

These measures demonstrate that Gjøvik has achieved significant reductions in damages from flooding events through the implementation of adaptation measures.

Total avoided damages for Gjøvik for the case of floods.

Direct	Short-term	SSP1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP5.85
No Solution implementation	8.0%	12.1%	12.7%	13.1%
With Solution implementation	6.7%			
Avoided damages	-16.6%	-44.7%	-47.3%	-48.8%
Indirect	Baseline (now)	SSP1.26	SSP 3.7	SSP5.85
No Solution implementation	5.0%	5.1%	5.3%	5.5%
With Solution implementation	2.0%			
Avoided damages	-59.5%	-60.3%	-62.2%	-63.2%

Figure 14: Avoided damages

Source: Gjøvik municipality and NCSR

4.0 Annex: Resources table

Step	Resource(s)
General resources	Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST) TransformAr Project web page IPCC Sixth Assessment Report Policy brief, understanding transformational adaptation Gjøvik municipality web page
Step 1 – Preparing the ground for adaptation	RAST Step 1 – Preparing the ground for adaptation TransformAr Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines TransformAr Stakeholder matrix and Innovation TransformAr Best practice – Stakeholder management TransformAr Playbook for transformational adaptation
Step 2 – Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities	RAST Step 2 – Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities TransformAr Playbook for transformational adaptation TransformAr Climate Impacts Portal TransformAr Economic evaluation of CC & loss damage functions TransformAr Climate cost assessment
Step 3 – Identifying adaptation options	RAST Step 3 - Identifying adaptation options TransformAr Playbook for transformational adaptation TransformAr Catalogue tool to identify best available solutions

4.0 Annex: Resources table

Step	Resource(s)
Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options	RAST Step 4 – Assessing and selecting adaptation options TransformAr Toolkit for adaptive action planning TransformAr Transformational adaptation scorecard TransformAr Avoided Damages Framework TransformAr Socio-economic impact tool TransformAr Results on the public acceptance and preferences TransformAr Report on willingness to pay for solutions TransformAr Sustainability profiles of solutions TransformAr Sustainability rating methodology
Step 5 – Implementing adaptation policies and actions	RAST Step 5 – Implementing adaptation policies and actions TransformAr Toolkit for adaptive action planning TransformAr Catalogue of solutions TransformAr Bankability reports
Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning	RAST Step 6 – Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning TransformAr Transformational adaptation scorecard TransformAr Avoided Damages Framework TransformAr Good practices and guidelines for avoiding damages TransformAr Socio-economic impact tool TransformAr Consolidation of TransformAr’s results

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